

FB (Fermat-Brahmagupta) Theorem

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Conditions:

$$F(n) = j^2 + k^2$$

(non-trivial representations as a sum of two squares)

$$j \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$$

$$k \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$$

$$j = 2x + 2$$

$$k = 2y + 1$$

$$F(n) = (2x+2)^2 + (2y+1)^2$$

$$F(n) = 4x^2 + 8x + 4y^2 + 4y + 5$$

$$F(n) = A * B \quad (A < B)$$

$$A = a^2 + b^2 \quad (a < b)$$

$$B = c^2 + d^2 \quad (c < d)$$

$$F(n) = 2^{2^n} + 1$$

$$e = 2^n$$

$$f = (e/2) - 1$$

$$g = 2^{**f}$$

THEOREM:

$$y = (a(x+g+1)) / b$$

$$y = ((c(x+g+1)) / d) - 1$$

Hereinafter, this theorem will be referred to as the FB Theorem. (**10.5281/zenodo.17874496**)